

http://plugin07.marketingdigitaltools.com/

NOVO TESTE

```

348         <img width="216" height
349     </div>
350 </div>
351     <div class="elementor-element elementor-element
352 <div class="elementor-widget-container">
353 <h3 class="elementor-heading-title elementor-size-m
354 </div>
355     <div class="elementor-element elementor-element
356 <div class="elementor-widget-container">
357         <div class="elementor-text-editor elementor
358 </div>
359 </div>
360     </div>
361 </div>
362 </div>
363     <div class="elementor-element elementor-element
364 <div class="elementor-column-wrap elementor-elemen
365     <div class="elementor-widget-wrap">
366     <div class="elementor-element elementor-element
367     <div class="elementor-widget-container">
368         <div class="elementor-image">
369             <img width="216" height
370         </div>
371     </div>
372     <div class="elementor-element elementor-element
373     <div class="elementor-widget-container">
374 <h3 class="elementor-heading-title elementor-size-
375 </div>
376     <div class="elementor-element elementor-elemen
377     <div class="elementor-widget-container">
378         <div class="elementor-text-editor elementor
379 </div>
380 </div>
381     </div>
382 </div>
383 </div>
384     </div>
385 </div>
    
```

Detetado WebSite

0 ERROS 0 AVISOS 2 ITENS

WebSite	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	1 ITEM
@type	WebSite				
WebSite	http://plugin07.marketingdigitaltools.com/				
potentialAction					
@type	SearchAction				
target					
@type	EntryPoint				
urlTemplate	http://plugin07.marketingdigitaltools.com/?s={search_term_string}				
query-input					
@type	PropertyValueSpecification				
valueRequired	http://schema.org/True				
valueName	search_term_string				